

Good practice report: selection of the best working solution for a novel biostimulant formulation

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The BIOSUVEG project

A challenge in the field of food security is developing strategies to grow crops productively, in increasingly extreme environments with less available resources. The use of organic inputs named biostimulants to enhance general crop performances has been subjected to ever intensive investigation in recent years, and more and more adopted in agriculture. The beneficial effects of biostimulants may include increasing crop yield and quality, improving tolerance and recovery from abiotic stress, and enhancing resource uptake and use efficiency. The research for new potential biostimulant components and their characterisation and usage optimisation represent challenging topics of research. In this context, the EIT Food innovation and research project “Innovative biostimulants for sustainable fruit production from vegetable crops (BIOSUVEG)” is being implemented. The main objective of the BIOSUVEG project is to launch on the market an innovative biostimulant, for improving phosphorus (P) and water use efficiency in crops. The EIT (European Institute of Innovation & Technology) Food is a European program of the previous Horizon 2020 Programme now included in Horizon Europe, that aims to accelerate innovation in the food system, financing also innovation projects to help start-ups, SMEs and other companies to launch innovative products on the market. The BIOSUVEG project is coordinated by Prof. Andrea Schubert from the University of Turin (IT) and involves a spin-off company from the University of Turin, StrigoLab Srl, which produces an innovative raw biostimulant ingredient. Other partners from industry and academia are also involved in the project, such as the agricultural cooperative Grupo AN (SP) and the Technical University of Munich (DE). In the frame of this project, we were asked to find the best working formulation for the raw biostimulant.

Biostimulant formulations

Strigolab’s raw biostimulant ingredient consists of a powder obtained from roots exudates of tomato plants following a proprietary process. The biostimulant ingredient was already tested during the Horizon2020 TOMRES project as two leaf sprays of a solution in acetone:water 1:100 at 10 g of powder/ha (1 ha being treated with 1000 L of solution). In the BIOSUVEG project, we aimed to formulate it to optimise its activity. Koppert Biological Systems B.V. (NL) kindly provided us with Formulation 1, a sticking agent obtained by blending innovative processing of urban waste, additives and other stabilizers and preservatives. Formulation 1 – based treatments are usually applied as leaf spray at 3 L/ha.

Therefore, 2 L of a raw biostimulant ingredient solution in Formulation 1 were prepared, to the final concentrations of 3 mL/L of Formulation 1 and 10 mg/L of the raw biostimulant ingredient in water. This solution was called Biostimulant 1:1. Then, 500 mL of this formulation were

dissolved in 500 mL of water (1:2 dilution). Finally, 200 mL of the 1:1 dilution were dissolved in 800 mL of water, generating a 1:5 dilution.

P starvation and drought trials

The biostimulant formulations were prepared as described in the previous section. Two different trials have been performed so far in tomato in pilot conditions (experimental greenhouse or plastic tunnel), testing the dilutions in two different stress conditions: P starvation (greenhouse trial performed by the University of Turin) and drought stress (protected field trial performed by the University of Turin and StrigoLab). For both experiments, two foliar applications were performed: the first one week after transplanting (at the stage of about 6 fully expanded leaves) and the second just before the first inflorescence appearance.

In the P starvation trial, seedlings of the tomato variety beefsteak “IMPERIUS F1” (Furia Seed) were transplanted in pots of 8 L of volume (filled with sand: vermiculite 50:50 by volume), and transferred to the greenhouse (Fig. 1A). The plants were watered with an automatic sprinkler system, supplying water for 2 min twice a day in each pot. Different P fertilization regimes were adopted by adding 1.26 or 0.63 g per plant of 19% Perphosphate (P_2O_5)-containing commercial fertilizer for 80 days of growth (+P and -P treatments, respectively).

In the drought trial, seedlings of the tomato variety beefsteak “GIGAWAK” (Syngenta) were transplanted in an open field under a plastic tunnel (Fig. 1B) located in Poirino (Turin, Italy). The plants were irrigated only once per month, vs thrice per month as the grower usually does in their facilities.

Figure 1A: Greenhouse P starvation trial in Grugliasco (Turin, Italy). **1B:** Drought stress trial under tunnel in Poirino (Turin, Italy)

A new biostimulant formulation for sustainable agriculture

The experiments highlighted that tomato plants treated with the 1:2 biostimulant formulation give higher yield in 80 days of greenhouse growth under both +P and -P regimes, with a slightly stronger effect under +P conditions (Fig. 2). A similar trend was also observed in mild drought stress conditions in protected field, with a positive effect of the biostimulant 1:2 on two months of cumulative yield (kg) per plant (Fig. 3). These results suggest that an application rate of two foliar sprays in tomato (right after transplant and during vegetative growth) with 5 g/ha of the StrigoLab’s raw biostimulant ingredient in combination with 1.5 L/ha of Koppert’s Formulation 1 increment yield in both +P and -P regimes, but with a slightly more evident effect under +P, and under drought stress in pilot conditions. Further work planned within the project will assess how far these effects can be replicated in a commercial growing environment.

Figure 2: Total yield (grams/plant) of plants grown in a greenhouse in Grugliasco (Turin, Italy) in +P or -P conditions (1.26 or 0.63 g P₂O₅ per plant, respectively, over the growth period of 80 days). Each bar represents the average of 4-6 replicate plants (var. beefsteak “IMPERIUS F1”, Furia Seed) with Standard Error. Different letters on top of bars indicate statistically different means (Tukey’s post-hoc test. P<0.05).

Figure 3: Total yield (kg/plant) of plants grown in open field (tunnel) in Poirino (Turin, Italy) under mild drought stress. Each bar represents the average cumulative yield per plant in two months (August-October) of harvest; $n = 15$ plants per treatment.

The following step of the BIOSUVEG project is to further test the biostimulant in the 1:2 dilution in open field in Spain, with the collaboration of Grupo AN, one of the largest agri-food cooperatives gathering farmers and ranchers in Spain. In particular, the biostimulant will be tested not only on tomato but also on pepper in drought stress conditions. Additionally, from these two trials, the quality of fruits will be assessed, with the collaboration of the Technical University of Munich. Finally, the University of Turin and StrigoLab will test again the 1:2 biostimulant formulation in +P and under salinity conditions in tomato in protected fields, in order to further confirm the positive effect observed.

In the near future, farmers will have to grow their crops under sub-optimal conditions, taking into account not only yield but also the consumers' demand for environmental sustainability. Biostimulants belong in the toolkit of the farmers, be they organic or integrated farming practitioners: rigorous testing is needed to optimise product formulation, make strict claims and meet farmers' expectations and needs. BIOSUVEG aims to make a contribution in this sense.

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